

Cushing, A. L., & Osti, G. (2023). “So how do we balance all of these needs?”: How the concept of AI technology impacts digital archival expertise. *Journal of Documentation*, 79(7), 12–29. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-08-2022-0170>

Supplementary materials

Focus Group 2-4 Prompts

NOTES FOR MODERATORS

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence (CC BY 4.0)

You are free to:

- Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format
- Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially

Under the following terms:

- Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the licence, and indicate if changes were made.

Full licence text: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

How to Use this PowerPoint

This PowerPoint can be used during the focus group to display questions and possible responses.

- **Prompt 1** - Display both scenario and questions
- **Prompt 2** - Display scenario; additional notes for moderator are for moderators to bring up if there is a lull in the conversation
- **Prompt 3** - Display scenario; additional notes for moderator are for moderators to bring up if there is a lull in the conversation

Please be mindful of time and make sure each scenario is addressed.

Prompt 1 Scenario

You have recently joined an organisation whose aim is to preserve images on various aspects of life in your country throughout the years. Your first project involves maintaining a series of images, from 1900 to 1925 capturing events in your capital city. One significant feature of this collection are images that aren't currently public. While the collection is extensive, several of the images haven't been digitized, with only a few photos available in jpeg format, of which very few carry extensive metadata (location, year, photographer, etc.).

A proposal has been put forward to use AI to help manage the photographs. Your line manager has asked you to partner with a development team to help create a system to help automate some of your work. You are given the opportunity to pick from three different areas that can be automated by an AI.

Prompt 1 Questions

1. The AI can automatically add descriptive data, telling you what is happening in the picture and transcribe any writing or identify any objects into legible searchable terms, helping with the time-consuming role of adding descriptive data manually
2. The AI can select which items from the collection are kept or not kept, doing away with information overload and only keeping the items considered most valuable to the collection in the online repository
3. The AI can help aggregate and sort items into categories and make connections between documents that otherwise would not have been made due to the scale of the overall collection

Which of these would you choose and why?

Prompt 2

Your supervisor now wants this automated system rolled out across the organisation, however you have noted that there is a perceived lack of trust for the new software among other colleagues in the institution. Your supervisor wants a forum to be held where these concerns can be addressed. Some of your colleagues air their grievances and are worried that:

- Potential redundancies or job losses
- Lack of training available to learn the new system
- Concerns over reliability of the new software and what happens if the software breaks or becomes obsolete

What concerns do you relate with the most and why? Do you have any additional concerns?

Prompt 2 - Additional Notes for Discussion

- Additional job duties in managing the system and fixing system errors rather than focus on core work
- Rigorous and long-term training that you don't feel is central to what you wanted out of your career
- Concerns over career path and if their role will become too niche for the broader job market
- What do digital curators think about working with AI computer scientists? Do they perceive a need of receiving help from AI experts, and do they feel they have something to teach in return?

Prompt 3

Your team is being featured in an online newspaper article. Part of the article addresses the fact that your team has been using AI technologies to great effect. However, the article highlights some public concerns, including privacy, transparency, and ethics of use of data that have been flagged about this technology.

What examples might the article use to highlight these key issues?

Prompt 3 - Additional Notes for Discussion

1. Transparency of data and an understanding of how the new software utilises data
 - a. How is this used in other cases outside of heritage – are people in danger of their data being used after they're gone and utilized for public use?
2. Privacy of data: regarding its safety, adherence to GDPR
 - a. Being that this is in Ireland, many people may have family members featured in the photos - how might that affect their privacy?
 - b. If your organisation has a modern collection of photos/blog posts/etc. from 2010-2020, are there permissions you would need to get before displaying this to the public?
3. Racial/cultural bias
 - a. Depending on how the metadata is coded, there could be a lot missed regarding the culture – does the AI know or understand the nuances of the conflict and appropriately code for the metadata